
Convert the System to the Economic Zones of the Environment Green

Ch. X. Qo'chqarova

Andijan machine building institute, b.f.f. PhD.

Abstract: Environmental crisis - the balance of the relationship between nature and society on a sustainable basis as a result of the violation of the condition of the progress of the deterioration in the natural environment, public administration and law enforcement of the situation arising out of the line and the loss of to restore the ecological system, that is, the natural environment and the social crisis, the environment is a disaster.

Key words: environmentally friendly, safe environment, the crisis of man's activities on the environment, anthropogenic effects, depletion of natural resources, environmental pollution and ecological systems.

Uzbekistan on measures to improve the state of the natural environment surrounding the works undertaken in spite of the level of ecological imbalances in society and the nature of the relationship is still in the development strengthening continues. This, first of all, to approach nature from the use of the enterprise, that is, the use of natural resources put the column of each organization only in its own interests and, secondly, as the only resource to look to nature, that is, the use of nature from the first level, the second level of protection at a glance we can see the quality of it. Nature is carried out using different means and methods of protection. Of them that most importantly - legal nature that is protected from pollution using the law of nature, xo'jasizlarcha use poison to protect it. Therefore, of particular importance in order to protect the rights of nature, rational use and protection of the nature of legal and physical persons it determines the order of the rules. Dedicated to the protection of nature in action in the law of environmental compliance requirements of environmental legislation applied in practice, providing the perfect qilinishini on them it is necessary to know. Because this is often caused by environmental law stems from the failure to follow them and knows not noxushliklar. For this reason, maintaining a healthy natural environment in many respects to the officials and citizens aware of the extent of compliance of environmental legislation and practice will depend on him.

The producers in the form of class society and the officials go in disputes between the state and the improvement of tools to work with to grow and feudal relations and the expansion of economic relations arising in the period of early capitalism in the form of market they came and evolved. The economic relationship between nature and society form-madaniyatlashgan only around of people to meet their needs not only economic economic and spiritual nature of consumer psychology position stand from environmental pollution as a result of use of resources and the reduction of human life, the nature of the system that lead to the change of style. A large area of the ecological system and in a large scale (global) a violation is observed. For the first time in the history of mankind in this period though, the emergence and development of the element legal, and religious institutions appear to be the source of legislation and other people in spite of the fact that the environmental awareness, knowledge and culture was very low. The law also in the qur'an also bound to avail of mankind in the bible is designed with the nature of the day of judgment. One of the stones in the pyramid in egypt, xeops, - "you cannot use line and from the power of human nature without understanding the true essence of the material world, they will perish", - was no accident that it is not [1;2;3].

The results of the survey. The period of scientific and technical achievements, it is not possible to maintain it in a safe environment environmentally, but the global armed conflict of the cold war and out the winners in a certain layer to enrich the population served. J. b. Lamarck 1820-1960 therefore also the year of "revolutionary sector to the development of" environmental security in the period of crisis was told that I have sudray towards the decisive period.

The effects of anthropogenic activities on the environment environmentally-safe environment so those three consequences of the crisis mujmui - depletion of natural resources, environmental pollution and ecological maxsuli is the disorder of the system.

The reduction of natural resources - a natural source of economic and other activity of the person, which are facilities that life is going to lose. According to the data of experts "human civilization" during the period, cut the part of business men in the forest during economic to'g'rirog'i madaniyatlashgan the globe consistently 2h3 I went down to 250 different types of animals and plants there went 3-4 billion. I sent hectares of agricultural land oborotga carried out, the atmospheric oxygen in the air of the reserves of 10 billion.tons decreased. In the next 100 years, the French scientist A. Gerrenning, according to data 2 billion anthropogenic soil erosion and disorder. sent hectares of land in the loss of fertility. These days, a 20-ha forest in the globe kesilmoqda in 1 minute per day, one type of animal or plant species are included into the red book.

In addition to the pollution of the environment from natural resources are reduced go a violation of the ecological system, matter and energy exchange in case natural night care has been affected dramatically. The pollution of natural substances that the natural environment (soil, water, underground riches, air...) of the content we will tell them to physical and chemical change. Such a change in the activities of human life in the night with you - anthropogenic pollution, in the night, without the participation of its natural pollution is called.

The total anthropogenic contamination of the environment pollution and economic relations in the form of 90-97%. is Natural substances and physical change in the city of industry, mainly in transport and at the expense of ximik (80-85 %), agriculture and agricultural tegralarda (70-85%) ximiyalashtirish, mexanizatsiyalash, build facilities and reclamation in addition to the number of livestock irrigatsion xaddan going to be increased at the expense of the hoof in a certain area are implemented. Tegralarida metallurgical industry is in a very high level of pollution and energy sectors [4;5;6].

Pollution of the environment and the natural processes and human activities in nature that the night without the direct participation of phenomena: the sun-space (meteorit the outpouring of magnetic storm); climate - hydrological (tayfun, storm, flood, weather, temperature and precipitation changes... least used falls back anomal); geological - geomorfologik (earthquake, sunami smaller horse structure is going to be a flood, snow to be moved, surilma, and the descent of the outbreak of the stone, these ice against azerbaijanis,...); geoximik (the eruption of natural gas under the ground, saline, poison botqoqliklarda out of gas, artificial materials... korrozitsiyasi); biological (qumursqa pests and the increase of mass, the result of the departure of the construction of the forest are on fire...). Environmentally safe economic effects to their environment in the form of 3-10% constitute. But the escalation of the level of pollution of the natural environment and anthropogenic effects on nature indirectly inflated from day to day is being sent. S. m. Myagkovning¹ of this change, according to the annual kofitsiyenti - 02,output -0.3, this section will change depending on the type of event and process.

The loss of natural resources and reduction of pollution, and the destruction of the ecological system and natural objects to come out of the ecological crisis will cause. Because of small and larger natural cycle of the ecological system or loss of any standing object in the chain of its features remain reduced as a result of environmental pollution nature is self-preservation, to resist external forces (buffer ministry) puts to lose and recovery properties [7;8;9]. The environmental crisis - the balance of the relationship between nature and society on a sustainable basis as a result

1 Menyayushiyasya mir: geograficheskiy podxod k izucheniyu. Sovetsko-amerikanskiy proyekt. Moskva-Arizona, 1991

of the violation of the condition of the progress of the deterioration in the natural environment, public administration and law enforcement of the situation arising out of the line and the loss of to restore the ecological system, that is, the natural environment and the social crisis, the environment is a disaster.

Around the aral sea environmental crisis is in his position and be an example to beneficially. The biggest lakes in the world Qachonlardir 30-40 years into the category of the aral sea is the most salty, polluted, and the people who remained the economic importance of the lakes has little to into the category of average. Syrdarya and Amudarya one of the main reasons for this drastic change of the water regime, that is, they come to put the year 1982-1983 12-13 times coming to the island the water is going to reduce. As a result, water levels 16 feet, 4 times reduced to 2 times the volume of water the surface of the water is gone. 3.3 million drained from the water surface.hectares deflyatsiya without make up (wind erosion) as a result of the pollution of the environment from thousands of miles of salt in the distance commanded, as a result of Amudarya and Syrdarya water of heavy metals, pesticides, herbicides and their use as water salinity as a result of contamination with chemicals such as suviniichimlik proven that they were professionals. Qachonlardir drained lakes and saline soil residual amudarya is a place to fish and hunt to become the center of what man was.

Conclusions. Between nature and society economic-ecological in the form of the relationship - to preserve the existing ones at the level of the ecological system is aimed at rational use of natural resources and environmental lifestyle.

The united states of america, Japan, Shvetsariya, germany, sweden legalist in countries such as the environmental ecological system is adapted to the shape of the relationship, the ones to'lig'icha quvvatlaniladi support any environmental measures by the state. The reduction of natural resources, pollution of nature, not only for citizens, but also for employees of state agencies also will profit neither material nor spiritual. For example, the us "national nature around protection policy" (NEPALI) according to the law, all legal and physical entities (governments also) will pass the test and confirmation test ago any natural object that can display different nature to the "application"shall submit to. The results of this test since the beginning of the 10 % "Applications" into the work of the court will remain. Environment protection at the council the president the executive committee of the council every month that come down to "Applications" and announced the decision of the court will open the list of references. Besides, the law on nature protection of every american to have the opportunity to take the united states buck himself. Because in the states legislative system determines there avvalam environmental condition to affect the local population.

The crisis of the natural environment, social environment not to bring ecological disaster in the near future we we need to take to form relationships.

The relationship between nature and society that shape ecological resources of nature to the ones we use most effectively, restore, and we understand the lifestyle aimed at the protection of nature. Such a lifestyle will lead to the improvement of the existing ecological system. There nobop state in the form of environmental attitude environmental management system is aimed at the restoration of avvalam areas and facilities. The technology of production here in the first place requires less chiqit or the case to be closed. The criteria of environmental consciousness and culture will become the defining factor in the person's role in society. Environmental laws and regulatory documents not only directly, but also indirectly to be based on the mechanism and practical application that requires full ekologiyalashtirilgan. Natural resources and natural objects to limit the use of "reconstruction" in a country that is not environmentally dangerous, but I object to special protection by the state is carried out on the territory and makes accessing to taqazo.

This particular should be noted that the nature and regulation of social relations associated with the use of legal measures aimed at the protection of them and their existing knowledge system of

the affected area at each historical stage, the development of science and technology, and the environment will depend on the level of the state of environment.

Therefore, we carried out in the twentieth century, scientific-technical revolutsiyasi created as a result of new technical tools, which in turn increased the production facilities to the effects of unintended negative environmental consequences of the conquest of nature protection.

Legal regulation of social and ecological relations, and has developed a system of measures aimed at is embarked on.

This is the level of environmental condition within the legal relations necessary for the emergence and development of environmental law and cognitive science to create.

Environmental law – the legal side of social relations that arise between society and nature, to learn to edit from the fund is also known as.

In today's independent environmental law of the republic of uzbekistan law and its place in the system that have the potential to be the particular direction and that it has the right properties in the area.

It should be noted in particular that the essence of each of the fields of law and regulation scope will depend on the level of social relationships. Including the area of environmental law the system of law as the social relations of the new regulation, the width of the complexity, diversity and the right area is distinct from other specific features.

Environmental law is also the nature-society system in the regulation of social relations in the first place of global importance, general ecological importance of the mandatory principles, methods and rules-use requirements, and secondly, to solve this complex environmental problems, their legal procedures in providing the strength and opportunities of other fields of law which are mutually associated uses. Because of the scale of the task to solve environmental problems focused on environmental law and the width of the society only reason priority and complex social, political, economic, spiritual and cultural measures in the spheres through the mobilization of the ecological relationships, you can edit all of the tools that are available.

THE LIST OF USED LITERATURE

1. Kuchkarova C. H. et al. The High Water Plants Water Road in Cleaning //Annual Research & Review in Biology. – 2019. – C. 1-5.
2. Habibullaevna K. C., Xodjakulov M. N. Emergency Situations that May Occur as a Result of Public Disorder, Damage Reduction and Fire Safety Measures //International Journal of Formal Education. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 12. – C. 74-77.
3. Habibullaevna K. C. Fuel Based on Food and Agricultural Organic Waste Development of Safe Technology of Briquettes //INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF BIOLOGICAL ENGINEERING AND AGRICULTURE. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 6. – C. 36-39.
4. Kuchkarova C. H. NATURAL DISTRIBUTION OF THE ALGAE PLANT OF THE TREATMENT OF TELEAROSOVODIS, SYSTEMATIC PLACE AND SEPARATE BIOLOGICAL FEATURES //Central Asian Problems of Modern Science and Education. – 2019. – T. 4. – №. 2. – C. 117-124.
5. Habibullaevna K. C., Mohinur N. MONITORING THE IMPACT OF INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES ON THE ENVIRONMENT //" ONLINE-CONFERENCES" PLATFORM. – 2022. – C. 285-288.
6. Habibullaevna K. C., Maftunakhan O. DEVELOPMENT OF SAFE TECHNOLOGY OF FUEL BRIQUETTES //" ONLINE-CONFERENCES" PLATFORM. – 2022. – C. 281-284.
7. Habibullaevna, K. C. (2023). Protection of Workers Sleep on Modern Solutions. *Miasto Przyszłości*, 43, 225-230.

8. Kh, K. C. (2023). Principles of Development of Engineering Ecology. *American Journal of Engineering, Mechanics and Architecture* (2993-2637), 1(10), 39-41.
9. Кучкарова, Ч. Х. (2023). СОВРЕМЕННОЕ СОСТОЯНИЕ ОХРАНЫ ОКРУЖАЮЩЕЙ СРЕДЫ В УЗБЕКИСТАН. *Mexatronika va robototexnika: muammolar va rivojlantirish istiqbollari*, 1(1), 85-87.
10. Kuchkarova, C., Jumanova, M., Tursunov, X., Urinova, S., & Nurmatov, J. (2023, June). Prospects for improving the technology of biological treatment of domestic and municipal waste water. In *AIP Conference Proceedings* (Vol. 2789, No. 1). AIP Publishing.
11. Habibullaevna, K. C. (2023). Analysis of Industrial and Environmental Safety Management Systems. *Best Journal of Innovation in Science, Research and Development*, 2(6), 211-214.
12. Kochkarova, C., Abdurakhmanov, A., Jumanova, M., Tursunov, H., & Jalilov, A. (2023). Analysis of urban communal water supply. In *E3S Web of Conferences* (Vol. 402, p. 09024). EDP Sciences.
13. Habibullaevna, K. C. (2022). MEASURES TO ENSURE NOISE AND VIBRATION SAFETY IN MANUFACTURING ENTERPRISES. In " *ONLINE-CONFERENCES*" *PLATFORM* (pp. 289-293).